

**DATA ANALYSIS IN DEVELOPING MED CARD SYSTEM
SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE AND DATABASE.**

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Annotation : If a medical institution has a medical information system that allows you to maintain a Med card, data from examinations, studies, and immunizations will be exported to the existing database. Thus, maintaining a Med card will allow you to analyze population data according to all the criteria of a medical card. Consistent filling of data by all institutions involved in assessing a person's health and treatment will allow doctors to have a complete basis for analysis and decision-making, and will eliminate the shortcomings associated with the loss of medical data, information about vaccinations, past diseases, etc. It will allow you to directly display life history data, rather than collecting it from the parents' words for each case of the disease. Standardization of types and classes will allow all participants filling out data in a medical record to analyze the development of a person as he grows older.

Keywords: Database, SQLite, NoSql, base, architecture, UML, Use Case, Object diagram.

Introduction

In today's world, where medical science and technology continue to advance at an astonishing rate, tracking patient records plays a key role in providing quality and effective medical care. Medical records are an integral part of health, providing a valuable source of information about the health of each patient. In society, the relevance of studying patient medical records is especially acute, given not only the rapid pace of development of medical science and technology, but also a number of challenges facing the healthcare system. The development of medical information

systems is a complex process that includes several key stages. Each stage has its own specificity and importance, and their correct implementation ensures the creation of effective and reliable software that can meet the needs of healthcare institutions and patients. It is important to consider that such systems must not only provide convenient access to medical information, but also ensure high data security and compliance with various standards and regulatory requirements.

Main Part

Below are the main stages of developing medical information systems that must be completed to achieve a successful result.

1. Define requirements

The first stage is the collection and analysis of system requirements. At this stage, it is necessary to understand what functions the system should perform, what data will be processed and how the interaction between the various components of the system will take place.

User Needs Analysis: Includes interviews with physicians, administrators, and patients to understand their needs and expectations.

Defining functional requirements: Listing required functions such as patient registration, medical history, report generation, etc.

Definition of non-functional requirements: Includes requirements for security, performance, reliability and usability of the system.

2. System design

At the design stage, the system architecture is developed, technologies and tools that will be used for development are determined.

Architectural design: Development of the overall system architecture, including client and server parts, databases and APIs.

User Interface Design: Create layouts of screens and interfaces to ensure ease of use.

Technical Design: Determining the technologies, programming languages, frameworks and libraries that will be used in the project.

3. System development

At the development stage, the actual writing of code, the creation and configuration of a database, as well as the integration of all system components take place.

Client side development: Creation of a desktop application for medical staff and a mobile application for patients.

Server side development: Creating a backend using the selected Django technology stack and Django Rest Framework.

Integration and Testing: Integrating all system components and conducting testing to identify and correct errors.

4. System testing

Testing is a critical step to ensure that the system operates correctly and meets all requirements.

Functional Testing: Testing all system functions to ensure they meet requirements.

Non-functional testing: Testing performance, security, reliability and usability.

User Testing: Conducting testing with end users to obtain feedback and identify potential problems.

5. System implementation

After successful completion of testing, the system is ready for implementation in a medical institution.

Deployment: Installing and configuring the system in a production environment.

User training: Conducting training and preparing educational materials for medical staff and administrators.

Support and Maintenance: Provide technical support and regularly update the system to fix errors and add new features.

6. Support and development

After the system has been implemented, the support and development stage begins, which includes regularly updating the system, adding new functions and

ensuring its stable operation.

Technical Support: Provide assistance to users when problems arise.

Updates and improvements: Regular system updates taking into account user feedback and changes in legislation and standards.

Monitoring and Analysis: Continuously monitor system performance and analyze data to identify opportunities for improvement.

One of the purposes of UML is to serve as a means of communication within the team and when communicating with the customer. Let's look at some possible uses for charts.

- Design. UML diagrams will help with modeling the architecture of large projects, in which you can assemble both large and smaller details and draw a skeleton (diagram) of the application. The code will subsequently be built on it.

- Reverse engineering - creating a UML model from existing application code, reverse engineering. Can be used, for example, on support projects where there is written code, but documentation incomplete or missing.

- Text information can be extracted from models and relatively readable texts can be generated—documented. Text and graphics will complement each other.

Use-case diagram

1. Actors

Patient: A user who can log in, view their medical history and download medical certificates.

Doctor: A user who can log into the system using a login and password issued by the superadmin, search for patients, view information about patients and their medical history, and add new diagnoses.

Superadmin: A user who registers healthcare workers, issues them logins and passwords, and also monitors the system.

2. Use cases (use cases)

Patient:

- Login

- View medical history
- Downloading online certificates about diseases

Doctor:

- Login using the login and password issued by the superadmin
- Patient search
- View information about the patient and his medical history
- Ability to add new diagnoses to the patient

Superadmin:

- Registration of health workers and issuance of login and password
- System monitoring

3. Interactions between actors and precedents

Patient:

- Login: The patient must be able to log in using their credentials.
- View medical history: After logging in, the patient can view their medical history.
- Downloading online certificates of diseases: The patient can download certificates of his diseases for personal use or provision to other institutions.

Doctor:

- Login using a login and password issued by the superadmin: The Doctor uses the credentials issued by the superadmin to log into the system.
- Patient search: The doctor can search for patients using various criteria (eg name, ID number).
- View patient information and medical history: After finding the patient, the doctor can view his medical history and current information.
- Ability to add new diagnoses to the patient: The doctor can add new diagnoses and update the patient's medical information.

Superadmin:

- Registration of medical workers and issuance of login and password: Superadmin registers new medical workers and provides them with credentials to access the system.

- System monitoring: Superadmin monitors the operation of the system, checks its condition and eliminates problems that arise.

4. Define system boundaries

Included:

- User authentication system (patients, doctors, superadmin).
- Functionality for viewing and downloading medical records and certificates.
- Functionality for searching patients and updating their medical data by doctors.
- Functionality for registering health workers and monitoring the system by superadmin.

Excluded:

- External systems such as laboratory information systems or external consultation systems.
- Functionality related to payment and billing processing.
- Any functionality related to the management of medical supplies.
- Integration with third party systems, except authentication (if not used).

Figure 1. Use-case diagram

In the diagram, these use cases will be depicted as ovals, and the actors will be represented as stick figures (for patients and doctors) and icons (for the superadmin). Lines will connect actors to their respective use cases, showing who can perform what functions.

Class diagram

Classes: List of main classes that will be used in the system.

Attributes and Methods: Define attributes and methods for each class.

Relationships: associations, aggregations, composition and dependencies between classes.

Inheritance: Class hierarchy and inheritance.

Class: User

• Attributes :

- id: int
- username:string
- password: string
- role: string

• Methods :

- login()

Class: Patient (inherits User)

• Attributes :

- medicalHistory: List[MedicalRecord]

• Methods :

- viewMedicalHistory()
- downloadMedicalCertificate()

Class: Doctor (inherits User)

• Attributes :

- specialty: string

• Methods :

- searchPatient()

- viewPatientInfo()
- addDiagnosis()

Class: SuperAdmin()

- Methods :
- registerDoctor()
- monitorSystem()

Class: MedicalRecord

- Attributes :
- recordId: int
- patientId: int
- doctorId: int
- diagnosis: string
- date: date

Figure 2. Class diagram

Data architecture in the context of databases describes how work with data is organized in a company. Its goal is to systematize this process by creating a database, setting up the data collection process, defining storage conditions and processing rules.

Conclusion

Based on our research and development, it can be concluded that this desktop application has enormous potential for use in healthcare settings to help improve healthcare delivery processes. Further development and improvement of the

application will contribute to further progress in the field of digitalization of healthcare and improve the quality of life of Pasitins.

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